

Advancing HPC Education: From Master's Programme to MOOC Platform for HPC Skill Development

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Abstract

High-Performance Computing (HPC) has significantly advanced in computational capabilities and applications transforming fields such as High-Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and Artificial Intelligence (AI). Innovation in HPC and the need for a well-trained workforce require educational institutions, including universities and lifelong learning centres, to evolve their curricula and training methods. Universities offering dedicated master's programmes around HPC are uniquely positioned to leverage their validated educational content and expertise in HPC research and education for this purpose. In this paper, we describe the development of an innovative Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) in HPC, drawing from our existing Master's Programme in HPC at the University of Luxembourg. We depict in detail the aspects of both courses, the Master's Programme in HPC, and the envisioned MOOC platform in HPC. While both courses encompass a shared body of knowledge, they differ substantially in their target audience, pedagogic opportunities, and skill level certification. Consequently, this divergence becomes fertile ground for a multitude of scientific inquiries and educational challenges, which we thoroughly explore and dissect in this paper. By addressing these issues, we provide the foundation for the successful development of a high-quality and high-impact MOOC in HPC for reskilling and upskilling, as well as democratisation to access specialised knowledge in HPC.

Keywords: High-Performance Computing (HPC), Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), Upskilling, Reskilling, Educational Innovation, Democratisation of Knowledge

1. Introduction

High-Performance Computing (HPC) has traditionally been the backbone of scientific research, powering complex simulations and computations that underpin significant scientific discoveries [1][2]. The impact of HPC advancements on High-Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been tremendous in areas ranging from climate modelling to genomics and from financial forecasting to advanced manufacturing [2].

The rapid evolution of these fields presents a significant challenge in terms of education and skill acquisition [3]. Traditional educational paradigms and frameworks, especially those prevalent in higher education institutions, often struggle to keep pace with these advancements [3]. For instance, the structure of master's programmes, while offering depth and rigour, may lack the agility required to adapt to the swiftly changing landscape of HPC, HPDA, and AI [4]. This widening gap between educational content and industry requirements has created a pressing need for alternative or complementary learning pathways that can facilitate the upskilling and reskilling of individuals, thereby aligning their competencies with current demands [4].

Addressing this need, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have emerged as a potent platform for delivering education in HPC, AI, and other technological fields through the delivery of online courses [4]. MOOCs stand out for their unparalleled flexibility and accessibility, qualities often challenging to achieve in traditional educational settings. Learners from diverse backgrounds and geographical locations will benefit from the cutting-edge HPC knowledge and expertise provided in the courses.

Creating a MOOC in HPC from scratch is a challenging endeavour [6]. However, universities and educational institutions already offering specialized master's programs in HPC are well-positioned to undertake this task. Leveraging their existing educational content and HPC expertise, these institutions can follow a MOOC design and development process more seamlessly [7]. This approach enables these institutions to bring proven quality and experience, as well as reputation and certification, to the development of MOOCs [8].

In this paper, we describe our methodology for developing an innovative MOOC in HPC, drawing from our existing Master's Programme in HPC at the University of Luxembourg. This process entailed a systematic adaptation of the Master's Programme's curriculum to formulate the MOOC framework, content and novel learning components. We depict the process of dissecting the Master's Programme to its fundamental HPC concepts, learning outcomes and skills,

and, based on the results, constructing the MOOC for a wide range of target audiences, providing different learning paths, and supporting innovative learning elements. We present a detailed analysis of the differences in the intended audience for the Master's Programme in HPC and the MOOC in HPC. For instance, the MOOC is designed to cater to a broader, potentially less specialised audience, influencing the pedagogic approach and complexity of the learning material. Nevertheless, it gives rise to opportunities for pedagogical innovation in HPC education, such as adaptive learning paths. We plan to study the efficacy of online learning for complex subjects such as HPC and investigate the scalability and sustainability of MOOCs. By exposing these challenges, the aim is to establish the foundation for the successful development of a high-impact and high-quality MOOC for HPC. Such a course will not only enhance individual skill development but also democratise access to specialised knowledge in HPC, thereby contributing to the overall advancement of the field.

2. Advancing HPC Education through Master's Programme and MOOC

This section explores the enhancement of HPC education through two distinct yet complementary platforms: master's programmes and MOOCs. Master's programmes represent the traditional educational route for in-depth HPC training, primarily targeting aspiring researchers, developers, and professionals in data and computation-intensive areas, such as system architects, system development and support, performance analysts and advisors, and data specialists. These programmes provide a comprehensive learning experience by integrating academic coursework with practical exposure gained through research projects, internships, and industrial connections. Recent trends indicate a growing emphasis on early-stage professional networking within these programmes. In contrast, MOOCs provide flexible, location-independent access to advanced HPC knowledge, democratising learning in this specialised field. They cater to a wide audience, transcending the constraints of location and background, and are instrumental in disseminating HPC skills across various proficiency levels.

2.1. Master's Programme in HPC

Traditional master's programmes in HPC have played a pivotal role in equipping students with essential skills for careers in both academic research and industry-specific roles. The rising demand for HPC expertise in both industry and academia has led to the creation of master's programmes with HPC specialisations at numerous global universities. For instance, the University of Southern California offers a master's in computer science emphasising HPC and simulation [9], and Northwestern University includes a High-Performance Computing specialisation [10] into its computer engineering master's programmes. Furthermore, institutions such as Sorbonne University [11] and the University of Luxembourg [12] offer dedicated master's programmes in HPC. Each university presents a unique curriculum, tailored to specific HPC focus areas. Other notable examples include the University of Edinburgh, known for its renowned HPC programme with applications in data analytics and scientific computing, and the KTH Royal Institute of Technology in Sweden and the University of Barcelona in Spain, which also offer programmes with strong emphases on computational science and HPC. These programmes are designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of HPC, covering its theoretical foundations, practical applications, and its increasing intersections with fields such as High-Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and Artificial Intelligence (AI).

The curriculum of the master's programme in HPC, HPDA, and AI [12] at the University of Luxembourg is organized into modules covering parallel programming, computational methods, system architecture, and performance optimisation. The programme is structured across thematic semesters, with the first focusing on foundational lectures, the second on core HPC topics, and the third on specialised lectures in HPC, HPDA and AI, respectively. Notably, the curriculum incorporates soft skills training encompassing aspects from entrepreneurship to proposal and project development. The programme concludes in the fourth semester, dedicated to thesis development. This comprehensive curricular approach ensures a thorough understanding of both hardware and software components of HPC systems. Pedagogical strategies include a mix of lectures, hands-on laboratory sessions, and project-based assessments, providing a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical skills development. Further details on the Master's Programme in HPC at the University of Luxembourg are presented in Section 3.

2.2. Massive Open Online Course in HPC

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) in HPC have demonstrated their value as effective tools for disseminating specialised knowledge to a diverse audience, overcoming geographical barriers and catering to individuals with varying educational backgrounds. The asynchronous nature of MOOCs introduces a flexible and accessible approach to HPC education. This adaptability enables swift adjustments to course content, aligning with the rapid development in the HPC field - a challenge often faced by traditional educational models with fixed curricula that can quickly become outdated.

MOOCs are designed to be regularly updated, ensuring that the material reflects the latest advancements and trends, including emerging topics such as LLMs and quantum computing. This dynamic nature keeps the course content

relevant and aligns with the fast-paced evolving of HPC. Interactive elements, such as video lectures, discussion forums, and virtual labs, contribute to engaging and immersive learning experiences within MOOCs. Additionally, their inclusive design caters to a broad spectrum of learners, from beginners seeking fundamental knowledge to professionals aiming to refresh their skills. This democratisation of HPC education expands its reach and accessibility. An additional advantage of MOOCs lies in their ability to provide certifications upon completion, adding tangible value to the learning process. This feature makes MOOCs a viable and attractive option for skill development and professional advancement in the dynamic field of HPC.

MOOCs in HPC exhibit diverse characteristics and cater different audiences. The utilisation of MOOCs has been recognised as an effective means of advancing HPC education. This recognition stems from the adaptable, accessible, and collaborative nature of MOOCs, coupled with their capacity for flexible learning paths [14][15][16]. Below is a non-exhaustive list of examples for MOOC related to HPC:

(1) FutureLearn provides an advanced, graduate-level online course focusing on using cloud computing for HPC workloads (called “High-Performance Computing in the Cloud”). This course covers a wide range of topics, from cloud architecture and infrastructure supporting HPC to the business opportunities enabled by HPC in the cloud.

(2) Coursera offers HPC courses curated by educational institutions and industries. These courses provide training suitable for individuals seeking personal growth and corporate teams looking for upskills in HPC.

(3) SWAYAM offers the course “High-Performance Computing for Scientists and Engineers,” specifically aimed at introducing HPC concepts to science and engineering students. It covers various parallel computing tools such as MPI, OpenMP, and CUDA, and relates them to domain-specific problems.

(4) UDACITY offers a high-performance computer architecture course that covers performance measurements, pipelining, and improved parallelism.

(5) ECMWF/IFAB: The European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) offers in partnership with the International Foundation on Big Data and Artificial Intelligence for Human Development (IFAB) a MOOC for machine learning in weather and climate [13].

2.3. Discussion on Master’s and MOOCs

Master's programmes in HPC offer a comprehensive educational experience within a structured learning environment that is challenging to replicate in an online format. The rigour of a master's curriculum, combined with direct interaction with faculty and peers, facilitates an immersive and social learning experience. Access to university resources, such as HPC facilities and research projects, further enrich the learning process. These programmes are particularly advantageous for individuals seeking thorough and in-depth education in HPC. The University of Luxembourg's master's programme in HPC has also fostered strong networking opportunities through workshops, internships, and industry-driven thesis development. This approach allows graduates to explore advanced research opportunities or take up specialised roles in the industry. On the other hand, MOOCs in HPC offer unparalleled flexibility and accessibility, enabling individuals to learn independently while balancing educational pursuits with other commitments such as work and family. The modular structure of MOOCs empower learners to tailor their educational paths based on their interests and skill levels. In addition, MOOCs can rapidly integrate new developments in HPC into their content, thereby ensuring up-to-date training. The choice between a Master's programme and a MOOC largely depends on the individual's learning objectives, career goals, and personal circumstances. Both pathways play pivotal roles in the evolving landscape of HPC education, addressing the diverse needs and preferences of learners worldwide.

3. Use case Master’s Programme in HPC at the University of Luxembourg

The Master in High-Performance Computing at the University of Luxembourg [12] is a two-year programme offering 120 ECTS credits, culminating in a Master's degree in HPC with specialisations in High-Performance Computing (HPC), High-Performance Data Analytics (HPDA), and Artificial Intelligence (AI). The curriculum [12] of the Master’s programme is meticulously structured to deliver comprehensive knowledge and skills in HPC, spanning four semesters, each with a unique thematic focus.

Semester 1 is dedicated to imparting fundamental knowledge and laying the groundwork for the programme. It includes modules in parallel programming, computational methods, system architecture, and performance optimisation, which are essential for building a robust foundation in HPC.

Semester 2 advances into more specialised topics, delving deeper into the complexities of HPC. This semester's curriculum is designed to provide students with an in-depth understanding of HPC, equipping them with specialised skills and knowledge. The first two semesters cover the following HPC topics:

Mathematical Methods and Statistics: Parallel numerical algorithms, linear algebra, linear programming, optimisation, numerical methods and analysis, probability, statistic estimation, data analysis, and design of experiments.

Software Engineering: Application life-cycle, application design methods and tools, component integration, software releases, software validation and verification, generic programming and code management tools.

Parallel Programming: Shared-memory and distributed memory, distributed systems, middleware technologies, parallel programming, operating system support, concurrency, synchronisation, parallelism, compiler and optimisations.

Computer Architecture: Processor architecture, memory hierarchy, pipelined and superscalar processors, structural control and data hazards, branch prediction, exception handling, devices, I/O, storage, networking, clusters, and cloud.

The third semester of the programme shifts focus towards the specialisations High-Performance Computing (HPC), High-Performance Data Analytics (HPDA), and Artificial Intelligence (AI). The third semester also includes modules on supplementary soft skills, balancing the technical aspects of the curriculum with skills essential for professional development. The final semester is predominantly focused on thesis development and completion of the programme. This phase involves working with a research initiative or industry collaborator, providing students with the opportunity to apply their academic knowledge in practical scenarios and gain valuable professional experience.

By completing the University of Luxembourg's specialization program, graduates will possess a diverse range of skills and competencies in HPC, preparing them for success in their respective fields. Although the specific skills may vary slightly among the specializations, they are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Categorisation of the learning outcomes of Master's programme in High-Performance Computing (HPC).

Category	Learning Outcomes
HPC and Artificial Intelligence/Data Analytics	Profound understanding of HPC in artificial intelligence and high-performance data analytics; Application of HPC in computational numerical analysis and multidisciplinary domains of machine learning, biotechnology, material science, physics, chemistry, and mechanics
HPC in Programming and Computing Technologies	Expertise in HPC-oriented parallel programming (GPU, FPGA); Knowledge of HPC applications in distributed systems, middleware technologies, and software engineering; Skills in HPC-centric compilers, compiler optimization, parallel programming design, parallel performance analysis; Understanding of quantum computing within the context of HPC
HPC in Software and Systems Engineering	Deep knowledge of HPC in the application life-cycle, including software stacks for CPU, GPU, FPGA CRGA; Expertise in HPC-related operating systems, kernel development, parallel file systems, high-speed networking, synchronization; Understanding of HPC's role in container technologies, virtualization, integration of HPC and cloud, server administration, infrastructure setup management & security
HPC in Hardware Design and Development	Broad understanding of HPC applications in SoC design, NoC design, microarchitecture, and memory systems; Knowledge in circuit design, power dissipation, low-power design techniques, thermal power models, all relevant to HPC hardware; Skills in HPC-related hardware aspects such as verification and test, reliability, multiprocessor design, accelerators (GPUs, FPGAs, CGRAs), application-specific architectures, hardware-software codesign, and cooling mechanisms related to HPC deployments
Transversal and Soft Skills in HPC Context	Proficiency in utilizing transversal and soft skills for adapting and integrating into various HPC sectors; Expertise in developing HPC-focused research topics, composing proposals, and employing critical evaluation and analytical skills; Competence in conducting HPC project risk assessments, managing potential failures, fostering learning environments; Aptitude for collaboration in diverse, multi-cultural HPC teams, fostering inclusivity, leveraging varied perspectives for improved outcomes

4. Design and Development Procedure for the MOOC in HPC

The envisioned MOOC must embody the essential qualities of the established Master's programme in HPC at the University of Luxembourg [12]. During the design sessions, two primary approaches for MOOC creation and evolution have been discussed: The first approach involves preserving the integrity of the learning content and transforming it, into modules for the MOOC. Consequently, each module would align with the structure and duration of the corresponding lecture. Although the required time and effort made this approach appealing, it may constraint the incorporation of innovative learning elements and methods facilitated by the MOOC educational platform.

Therefore, we opted for a second approach, with the development of the MOOC guided by the transfer of skills and learning outcomes obtained upon the successful conclusion of the Master's programme. This strategy provides MOOC designers with increased flexibility and, notably, the opportunity to incorporate innovative learning elements. On the other side, this approach demands a more substantial effort to understand the learning goals and skills, accurately translating them into appropriate MOOC content, and organising the MOOC structure accordingly. One benefit is that the curriculum needs less frequent updates. This may become more critical, especially in rapidly evolving fields (e.g. Application Domain Experts).

An overview of the MOOC development procedure based on the underlying master's programme in HPC is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. The development procedure is designed to transfer the Master's quality to the MOOC.

The Master's Programme consists of thematic modules, which are again a collection of lectures. A distinguished lecturer generally provides each type of lecture. Therefore, the entire learning content, including slides, exercises, assignments, and references, of the Master's Programme needs to be first aggregated for further processing. The next step is to distil skills contained in the learning content of the master's programme and map them to a body of knowledge reference framework for HPC. This procedure can be realised using various methods (e.g., graph matching), and the results will vary depending on the method or reference framework used. A solid HPC body of knowledge reference framework is provided by the HPC Certification Forum (HPC-CF) [19], which we chose. HPC-CF has developed over 300 skills, classifying and defining competence standards for HPC. It focuses on standardising the knowledge representation in HPC into fine-grained competencies. The forum has been instrumental in creating a common language and in understanding HPC roles and the associated skills required for HPC practitioners.

Once the Master Programme learning content/curriculum is mapped to the skills of the reference framework, the focus can shift to designing the MOOC skill and learning outcomes following the procedure illustrated in Fig 2.

Figure 2. Skills transferred from the Master's programme must be distilled and mapped to an HPC body of knowledge reference framework to create learning content specifically for the MOOC in HPC.

5. MOOC in HPC: Framework and Innovations

Our approach is guided by the RASE pedagogical course design model, with the extensive inclusion of innovative measures. The module is divided into three learning sections. Each section is generally structured according to a template but can adapt to best address the structure and function of the learning content. The section hierarchy allows learners to learn busy schedules at shorter intervals. Additionally, the section sub-structure allows for a more homogenous content delivery, alternating, complementing, and synergising between HPC-focused- and application-

focused content. The proposed innovative Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) in HPC has a diverse audience, ranging from professionals seeking upskilling or reskilling to jobseekers, consultants, entrepreneurs, and both current and future users of HPC must be considered and covered. The following subsections outline the key components of our MOOC structure and framework, detailing how each element contributes to an effective and engaging learning experience.

5.1 Structure, Framework and Characteristics

Our MOOC is specifically for professionals at various stages of their careers, jobseekers, consultants, entrepreneurs, and HPC users. This broad target audience ensures that the course is relevant and beneficial for individuals with different professional backgrounds and objectives, whether they are looking to enhance their current skills or acquire new ones in the HPC field.

Each section of our MOOC is rich in content, featuring text accompanied by visual elements, such as graphs, charts, and images. These visual aids are integral to understanding complex concepts and providing learners with a more comprehensive and engaging educational experience.

The course is structured into sections, each lasting 30 minutes, and modules comprising three sections, totalling 90 minutes. This duration was carefully chosen to ensure that the course was suitable for busy professionals and job seekers. Our MOOC features sections associated with tiers ranging from one to three. This tiered approach allows learners to learn topics at varying depths and focuses on their current knowledge levels and learning objectives. This flexibility ensures that the course remains accessible and challenging for all the learners. We plan to incorporate domain-specific sections into the MOOC, offering learners the option of increasing their focus on particular domains of interest. This feature is particularly beneficial for those who wish to apply HPC knowledge to specific fields or industries.

The structure of our MOOC is highly adaptable, and accommodates different levels of content complexity, learner proficiency, and educational goals. The key to this adaptability is maintaining logical coherence and clear progression throughout the course, ensuring that learners can easily follow and build upon the acquired knowledge.

Webinars are an integral part of our MOOC, facilitating social learning and reinforcing the knowledge gained through asynchronous and virtual learning platforms. These live sessions provided an opportunity for learners to interact with experts and peers, deepening their understanding and engagement with the course material.

5.2 Tiers: Educational Pathways

Our tier-based approach presents a structured educational framework designed for a wide range of individuals with varying levels of expertise and interests in HPC. We segmented the MOOC into three distinct tiers: Fundamental, Advanced, and Expert, as explained below.

Fundamental Tier. This tier targets individuals interested in HPC, including data specialists, high-level users and policymakers. The prerequisite for this tier is an introductory understanding of data science principles, with no prior knowledge of HPC required. The learning outcomes focus on providing foundational knowledge in HPC technology, understanding the basic data value chain in these sectors, and the ability to identify key applications and technologies that drive innovation.

Advanced Tier. This tier is aimed at specialists with background in HPC. The expected audience includes academia, research institutes, data consultants, and users interested in these fields. Prerequisites include the successful completion of Tier 1 or equivalent experience in HPC, along with familiarity with basic programming concepts and data analysis. The learning outcomes for this tier involve developing an understanding of the HPC system architecture, GPU programming, and their specific applications. Learners will be prepared to tackle complex data challenges and contribute to technological advancements in this field.

Expert Tier. The third tier was designed for experts seeking a deep understanding of HPC systems, GPU programming, and their applications. Completion of Tier 2 or substantial experience with HPC systems is required, along with proficiency in advanced programming and data-analysis techniques. The learning outcomes for this tier include mastering HPC, utilizing advanced computational methods and data analysis to solve complex problems, and the ability to innovate and lead projects using HPC technology.

5.3 From Balancing Modules to Levelled Knowledge

Creating training programmes for HPC users with varied educational backgrounds is a challenging task. New users often lack a common set of foundational skills, which makes it challenging to design one-size-fits-all courses. Existing users must adapt to new tools and knowledge, leaving established workflows in favour of more efficient ones. Additionally, the absence of standardised criteria for evaluating HPC training courses and defining user competence adds complexity. Therefore, master programmes often rely on dedicated modules, so-called balancing modules, to address diverse backgrounds. Balancing modules in the Master's Programme in HPC provides support to students with a non-computer science bachelor's degree. These balancing modules contain introductory materials for various subjects to

enable non-computer science students to proceed with more advanced topics. Because of the nature of balancing modules, depending on the programmes offered at the teaching institutions, the balancing modules might need to be prepared, but might not be attended to their full capacity because they address only a subset of the HPC Master Programme students, or worse, only a minimum of students are attending them. To bring the function of the balancing modules to an MOOC, we propose a mechanism called levelled knowledge.

Levelled knowledge for MOOC courses is proposed as a dynamic component, and the student can adjust the depth level for lower or deeper understanding depending on the pre-knowledge and background, and repeat the material until the desired knowledge depth level is mastered. Although providing a more convenient way to adapt faster and adjust better to the desired knowledge depth, levelled knowledge for MOOCs comes with higher preparation costs compared to a traditional MOOC; however, it might be lower than the costs (preparation/attending) of balancing modules, depending on how many balancing modules need to be preprepared for how many potential attendees.

5.4 Adaptive Learning Paths via Knowledge Graphs

Prerequisites serve as pre-conditions for entering and progressing in the Master's programme. MOOCs, on the other side, can use AI to assess and verify pre-existing knowledge and skills of MOOC participants. The resulting knowledge graph for everyone enables AI to create highly personalised learning pathways. The concept of knowledge graphs in this context refers to a comprehensive mapping of a learner's existing skills and knowledge [16][17]. Knowledge graphs can be dynamically updated as the learner progresses, thereby providing real-time insights to the learner and assessor. By tailoring the learning material to match an individual's current understanding and skill level, MOOCs can become significantly more efficient. Learners would no longer need to wade through familiar materials, allowing them to focus their efforts on areas that require further development. This not only saves time, but also enhances the learning experience, keeping learners engaged and motivated. Additionally, the adaptive nature of this approach means that as a learner's skills and understanding evolve, so too does the learning path, ensuring that educational content remains relevant and challenging.

5.5 MOOC Sustainability

For any sustainable educational program, rapid technological evolution and changing educational paradigms must be considered in their design to increase its sustainability and lifetime, and thus its usefulness. For instance, rapid changes in the HPC landscape may make parts of the curriculum outdated earlier than other parts [21][22]. Furthermore, changes in educational trends or student interests must be frequently assessed and considered. To address these challenges, it is essential to incorporate flexible and modular course designs that can be easily adapted. By dividing modules into comprehensive and integral topics, rather than fixed durations, educators can respond more effectively to evolving educational needs. The development of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), such as one designed for Brazilian healthcare providers working with substance use disorders [8], highlights the significance of conducting a needs assessment when determining course content and maintenance. This process involves gathering data from multiple sources, including literature reviews, expert panels, and focus groups, to ensure that the course material remains relevant and to address specific skill gaps in the workforce. Adopting this approach is crucial for creating MOOCs that are both pertinent and capable of managing the evolving demands of the target audience.

6. Comparative Analysis between Master's Programme and MOOC in HPC

Summarising, based on our elaborations in this paper detailing the Master's Programme and the proposed MOOC in HPC, we present a table with a comparative analysis of the differences and similarities of both HPC education programmes (Table 2). While some aspects are of reasonable choice, such as the section duration, other aspects are a result of the inherent characteristics of Master's and MOOCs, respectively.

Table 2. Comparative analysis of both HPC education programmes, Master's and MOOC.

	Master's Programme in HPC	MOOC in HPC
Structure	Two-year program, 120 ECTS, focuses on parallel programming, computational methods, and specialisation in HPC, HPDA, and AI.	Varies, typically 4-12 weeks per course, modules with Fundamental, Advanced, Expert tiers, each section lasting 30 minutes.
Number of Courses	Approximately 20-30 courses, including core subjects, electives, and thesis/research project	Varies, usually 5-10 modules per tier (Fundamental, Advanced, Expert)
Target Audience	Aspiring researchers, developers in data and computation-intensive areas.	Broad audience, including professionals and jobseekers, with or without prior HPC knowledge.
Learning Outcomes	Comprehensive understanding of HPC, skills in parallel programming, system architecture, In-depth knowledge across a broad spectrum of HPC disciplines, readiness for research or industry roles in computational sciences.	Foundational to expert knowledge, adaptable learning paths, specific skills in HPC applications, with flexibility to specialise in areas of interest. Suitable for professional development or skill enhancement.
Pedagogical Approaches	Lectures, hands-on labs, project-based assessments, soft skills training, seminars, and project work.	Online learning, interactive elements like video lectures, forums, quizzes; live sessions.
Certification	Master's degree, specialisation in HPC, HPDA, AI.	Certificates upon completion, potential for micro-credentials or badges in specific HPC skills or tools.
Flexibility	Full-time, two years.	Self-paced, accessible anywhere.
Cost	Tuition fees, potentially higher for external students.	Often free or low-cost, fees for certification.
Access to Computing Resources	Direct access to high-performance computing facilities and labs	Access to virtual labs and cloud-based HPC resources for practical exercises
Professional Networking	Opportunities for internships, industry projects, and academic collaborations	Online communities, webinars, and interaction with instructors and peers worldwide

Table 2 shows a structured comparison across several dimensions, including the structure, number of courses, target audience, learning outcomes, pedagogical approaches, certification, flexibility, cost, access to computing resources, and professional networking opportunities. The Master's Programme is a two-year programme with a comprehensive curriculum focusing on parallel programming, computational methods, and specialisations in HPC, HPDA, and AI. It targets aspiring researchers and developers in data and computation-intensive areas, offering 20-30 courses, including core subjects, electives, and a thesis/research project. The pedagogical approach is traditional, with lectures, labs, and project-based assessments, leading to a Master's degree with a specialisation in HPC, HPDA, and AI. In contrast, the MOOC in HPC is designed to be more flexible, catering to a broader audience, including professionals and jobseekers with varying levels of prior HPC knowledge. It is structured into modules across Fundamental, Advanced, and Expert tiers, each lasting 30 minutes, and can span 4-12 weeks per course. The MOOC offers a modern pedagogical approach with online learning, interactive elements, and certificates upon completion.

In summary, both educational programmes share the goal of advancing HPC education but differ in their delivery, audience, and flexibility, highlighting the University of Luxembourg's commitment to addressing diverse learning needs and preferences in the evolving field of HPC.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

The High-Performance Computing (HPC) sector has adopted various educational strategies to train scientists and engineers to leverage parallel and distributed computing systems to enhance their research and development activities. Despite these initiatives, the uptake of HPC within the broader scientific and engineering communities still needs to be improved. A significant barrier to wider adoption is the steep learning curve associated with HPC. To support these professionals effectively, it is crucial to tailor educational content to their specific needs and simplify HPC concepts to make them more accessible. MOOCs are essential in HPC education because of their ability to keep pace with the rapid advancements in the field, provide broad access to cutting-edge knowledge, foster a global learning community, and offer flexible learning tailored to individual skill levels. This paper proposed a procedure for designing and evolving contemporary MOOC teaching using traditional HPC training techniques, such as HPC-related master programmes.

To leverage the potential of MOOCs for HPC, we described in this paper innovative teaching elements designed specifically for a MOOC in HPC. We proposed a tiered approach to allow learners to customise their learning path according to their knowledge and skill levels. Advanced learners can rapidly progress to more complex topics, ensuring that they are constantly challenged and engaged. This flexibility is crucial in fields such as HPC, where the range of expertise can vary significantly among learners. Moreover, we propose to overcome the limitations of current one-size-fits-all models by introducing adaptive learning paths tailored to the unique knowledge and skill profiles of each learner. This approach promises to deliver a more efficient and personalised educational experience.

The next phase consists of the full implementation of the MOOC. Following this, we will conduct thorough evaluations to refine course content, ensuring it meets the diverse needs of learners and aligns with the latest HPC advancements. This pilot phase will also allow for optimising interactive elements and feedback mechanisms, enhancing the overall learning experience and engagement within the MOOC platform. Insights gained from these initial runs will be instrumental in scaling the MOOC to accommodate a larger, global audience, aiming to bridge the gap of HPC education and industry, while fostering a community of skilled professionals in HPC.

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